

Research Article

Heat Source and Radiation Absorption Effects on Heat Mass Transfer Flow with
Variable Thermal Conductivity

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Abstract

The present study investigates the fully developed natural convection flow of dissipative radiative fluid over an infinite vertical porous plate in the presence of transverse magnetic field and variable thermal conductivity taking into account the effects of heat source/absorption and radiation absorption. The governing equations are coupled and highly non-linear which defy analytical solution and were solved numerically using the implicit finite difference scheme. The results of the computations for velocity, temperature and concentration distributions are displayed graphically for different values of the governing parameters while the Skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number are presented in tabular form.

Keywords: Heat Transfer, Mass Transfer, Variable Thermal Conductivity, Heat Source, Radiation Absorption.

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Introduction

The study of flow problems which involve the interaction of several phenomena has a wide range of applications in the field of Science and Technology. There are several transport processes in industry and in nature where buoyancy force arises from both thermal and mass diffusion, which are caused by the temperature gradients and the concentration differences of dissimilar chemical species. Hence, this analysis deals with the free convection flows driven by temperature gradients and concentration

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differences. When the free convection occurs at high temperatures, radiation effects, variation of viscosity with temperature and variation of thermal conductivity of the fluid cannot be neglected. Nuclear power plants, missiles, gas turbines and space vehicles are examples of such engineering areas. Kishore *et al.* (2010) investigated the effect of viscous dissipation and thermal radiation on MHD heat and mass diffusion flow past a surface embedded in a porous medium. The study of fluid flows is of paramount importance in engineering. The fluid flow can also be found in electronic engineering such as cooling of electronic equipment ranging from individual transistor to mainframe computers. Also in agricultural processes, foods are dried and preserved under variable temperatures as well as in nuclear plants, missiles, gas turbines and various propulsion devices for aircraft.

The unsteady free convection flow along a vertical plate received considerable interest because of its application in devices which are cooled by natural convection as in the case of electrical heaters and transformers. Reddy *et al.* (2009) studied the unsteady magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) convective heat and mass transfer flow past a semi-infinite vertical porous plate with variable viscosity and thermal conductivity assuming that the viscosity of the fluid varies as an inverse linear function of temperature. Numerical study on a vertical plate with variable viscosity and thermal conductivity has been reported by Palani and Kim (2010). The Crank-Nicolson type of finite difference scheme was used in the work. An isothermal vertical plate was immersed in a fluid with free convection.

The study of combined heat and mass transfer with chemical reaction is very vital in many processes such as energy transfer in a wet cooling tower, drying and dehydration operations in chemical food processing plants, gas industries and combustion of atomized liquid fuels. In order to use this model to study fluid flow when applied to grain storage, the working fluid is always air. On the other hand, a chemical reaction occurs between a foreign mass and a fluid. The chemical reaction can be codified either homogeneous or heterogeneous processes. Its effect depends on the nature of the reaction whether the reaction is homogeneous or heterogeneous. Prakash *et al.* (2010) studied the effects of thermal diffusion and chemical reaction on MHD flow of dusty viscoelastic (walter's liquid model-B). Sharma and Deka (2012) investigated chemical reaction effects on MHD mixed convection flow of water at maximum density past a vertical plate under variable temperature. Chambre and Young (1958) studied diffusion of chemically reactive species in a laminar boundary layer flow. A study of induced magnetic field with chemically reacting fluid past a vertical permeable plant was investigated by Ahmed (2011) while Ahmad and Zueco (2010) investigated combined heat and mass transfer by mixed convection MHD flow along a porous plate with

chemical reaction in the presence of heat source. The effect of the chemical reaction and radiation absorption on the unsteady MHD free convection flow past a semi infinite vertical permeable moving plate with heat source and suction was studied by Ibrahim *et al.* (2008). Their finding showed that, the velocity profile increases with decreasing permeability parameter.

The aim of the present study is to investigate the effect of dissipation, chemical reaction, radiation absorption, heat source and thermal radiation parameters as well as Prandtl, Schmidt, thermal Grashoff and mass Grashoff numbers on unsteady MHD flow over an infinite vertical porous plate with temperature dependent thermal conductivity and viscosity. The dimensionless governing equations which are coupled and non-linear were solved numerically using the implicit finite difference scheme. This method has been extensively developed in recent years and remains the simplest as well as one of the best methods for solving partial differential equations. The effects of all the governing parameters on the heat and mass transfer are discussed carefully for selected values of the parameters.

Problem Formulation

Consider the flow along an infinite vertical plate that is embedded in a porous medium. Let u' and v' be the velocity component along the x' - and y' -directions respectively. If x' - axis is chosen along the plate in the vertically upward direction and y' - axis perpendicular to it, then the investigated flow does not depend on x' . Such laminar flow with temperature dependent variable viscosity and thermal conductivity along a vertical porous plate under the Boussinesq approximations has the continuity equation as

$$\frac{\partial v'}{\partial y'} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Initially, the plate and the fluid are at same temperature T'_∞ with concentration level C'_∞ . At time $t' > 0$, the plate temperature and the mass concentration is raised to T'_w and C'_w causing the presence of temperature and concentration difference $T'_w - T'_\infty$ and $C'_w - C'_\infty$ respectively. It is assumed that both the thermal conductivity and the n th order chemical reaction are not constant and the MHD term is derived from an order-of-magnitude analysis of the full Navier-Stokes equations while the porous medium is regarded as an assembly of small identical spherical particles fixed in space. Under these conditions and assuming variation of density in the body force term (Boussinesq's

approximation), the governing equations of momentum, concentration and energy for the unsteady flow can be written as

$$\frac{\partial u'}{\partial t'} + v' \frac{\partial u'}{\partial y'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(\tilde{\nu} (T') \frac{\partial u'}{\partial y'} \right) - \frac{\dagger B_0^2 u'}{\dots} - \frac{\tilde{\nu} (T') u'}{k^*} + g S (T' - T'_\infty) + g S^* (C' - C'_\infty) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial C'}{\partial t'} + v' \frac{\partial C'}{\partial y'} = D \frac{\partial^2 C'}{\partial y'^2} - R^* (C' - C'_\infty)^n \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial T'}{\partial t'} + v' \frac{\partial T'}{\partial y'} = \frac{1}{\dots C_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \left(K (T') \frac{\partial T'}{\partial y'} \right) - \frac{1}{\dots C_p} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y'} + \frac{\tilde{\nu} (T')}{C_p} \left(\frac{\partial u'}{\partial y'} \right)^2 + \frac{Q_1 (T' - T'_\infty)}{\dots C_p} + Q_0 (C' - C'_\infty) \quad (4)$$

Subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$\left. \begin{aligned} t' \leq 0, \quad u' = 0, \quad T' = T'_\infty, \quad C' = C'_\infty & \quad \text{for all } y' \\ t' > 0, \quad u' = 0, \quad T' = T'_w, \quad C' = C'_w & \quad \text{at } y' = 0 \\ u' \rightarrow 0, \quad T' \rightarrow T'_\infty, \quad C' \rightarrow C'_\infty & \quad \text{as } y' \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\nu}$ is the kinematic viscosity of the grey fluid, \dagger is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, B_0 is the constant magnetic field intensity, \dots is density, k^* is the permeability, g is the gravitational constant, β is the thermal expansion coefficient, S^* is the concentration expansion coefficient, T' is the temperature, C' is the mass concentration, D is the chemical molecular diffusivity, R^* is the chemical reaction, C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure, q_r is the radiative heat flux, u' and v' are velocity components in x and y directions respectively, t' is time, $K(T')$ is the thermal conductivity, $\tilde{\nu}(T')$ is the viscosity, Q_1 is the dimensional heat source/absorption coefficient, Q_0 is the coefficient of proportionality for the absorption of radiation and n is the reaction order while T'_w is the wall temperature, T'_∞ is the free stream temperature, C'_w is the species concentration at the plate surface, C'_∞ is the free stream concentration.

From the continuity equation (1), it is clear that the suction velocity is either a constant or a function of time. Hence, on integrating equation (1), the suction velocity normal to the plate is assumed in the form, $v' = -\epsilon_0$ where ϵ_0 is a scale of suction velocity which is non-zero positive constant. The negative sign indicates that the suction is towards the plate and $\epsilon_0 > 0$ corresponds to steady suction velocity normal at the surface.

Assuming the radiative heat flux from the Rosseland approximation to have the form

$$\frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y'} = -4\ddagger a^* (T_\infty'^4 - T'^4) \quad (6)$$

where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, a^* is the mean absorption effect for thermal radiation constant. Assuming that the temperature differences within the flow are sufficiently small such that T'^4 can be expanded in a Taylor series about T_∞' and neglecting higher order terms gives

$$T'^4 \cong 4T_\infty' T'^3 - 3T_\infty'^4 \quad (7)$$

It is assumed that the fluid viscosity $\sim(T')$ and thermal conductivity $K(T')$ are linear functions of temperature following Lai and Kulacki (1991)

$$\sim(T') = \sim_\infty \{1 - \chi(T' - T_\infty')\}, \quad K(T') = k_0 \{1 + \chi(T' - T_\infty')\} \quad (8)$$

Method of Solution

To solve the governing equations in dimensionless form, we introduce the following non-dimensional quantities:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \frac{u'}{U_0}, \quad y = \frac{y'U_0}{\sim_\infty}, \quad t = \frac{t'U_0^2}{\sim_\infty}, \quad \eta = \frac{T' - T_\infty'}{T_w' - T_\infty'}, \quad C = \frac{C' - C_\infty'}{C_w' - C_\infty'}, \quad \ddagger = \chi(T_w' - T_\infty'), \quad r = \frac{\epsilon_0}{U_0}, \quad H = \frac{Q_1 \sim_\infty}{\dots c_p U_0^2}, \\ Sc &= \frac{\sim_\infty}{D}, \quad Pr = \frac{\sim_\infty \dots c_p}{k_0}, \quad Ec = \frac{U_0^2}{c_p (T_w' - T_\infty')}, \quad Gr = \frac{g S \sim_\infty (T_w' - T_\infty')}{U_0^3}, \quad Gc = \frac{g S^* \sim_\infty (C_w' - C_\infty')}{U_0^3}, \\ K &= \frac{k^* U_0^2}{\sim_\infty^2}, \quad N = \frac{16a\ddagger T_\infty'^3 \sim_\infty}{k_0 U_0}, \quad M = \frac{\sim_\infty \ddagger B_0^2}{\dots U_0^2}, \quad Kr = \frac{\sim_\infty R^* (C_w' - C_\infty')^{n-1}}{U_0^2}, \quad Q = \frac{Q_0 \sim_\infty (C_w' - C_\infty')}{U_0^2 (T_w' - T_\infty')} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The governing equations on using (9) into (1), (2), (3), (5) and using (6) - (9) into (4) reduce to

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} - r \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} = (1 - \ddagger \eta) \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} - \ddagger \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} - MU - \frac{(1 - \ddagger \eta)}{K} U + Gr_\eta + GcC \quad (10)$$

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$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} - r \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{Sc} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} - KrC^n \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - r \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} = \frac{(1+\ddagger)}{Pr} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\ddagger}{Pr} \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \frac{(H-N)}{Pr} \theta + Ec(1-\ddagger) \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)^2 + QC \quad (12)$$

The initial and boundary conditions become

$$\begin{aligned} t \leq 0, \quad U = 0, \quad \theta = 0, \quad C = 0 & \quad \text{for all } y \\ t > 0, \quad U = 0, \quad \theta = 1, \quad C = 1 & \quad \text{at } y = 0 \\ U \rightarrow 0, \quad \theta \rightarrow 0, \quad C \rightarrow 0 & \quad \text{as } y \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where Pr is the Prandtl number, Sc is Schmidt number, Ec is Eckert number, Gr is thermal Grashof number, Gc is mass Grashof number, M is magnetic field, K is porosity, N is the radiation, r is suction, ‡ is the thermal conductivity, Kr is the chemical reaction, n is the reaction order, H is heat source/absorption and Q is the radiation absorption, parameters.

Numerical Procedure

Equations (10) - (12) are unsteady coupled non-linear partial differential equations and are to be solved under the initial and boundary condition of equation (13). However, exact or approximate solutions are not possible for these set of equations and hence were solved by the implicit finite difference scheme. Equations (10) - (12) gives

$$-q_1 r_1 U_{i-1}^{j+1} + (1+2q_1 r_1) U_i^{j+1} - q_1 r_1 U_{i+1}^{j+1} = q_1 r_2 U_{i-1}^j + (1-2q_1 r_2 - \chi r_3 - r_4 - q_1 r_5) U_i^j + (q_1 r_2 + \chi r_3) U_{i+1}^j - q_1 r_3 \ddagger (\theta_{i+1}^j - \theta_i^j) (U_{i+1}^j - U_i^j) + \Delta t Gr_{\theta i}^j + \Delta t Gc C_i^j \quad (14)$$

$$-r_1 C_{i-1}^{j+1} + (Sc + 2r_1) C_i^{j+1} - r_1 C_{i+1}^{j+1} = r_2 C_{i-1}^j + (Sc - 2r_2 - \chi r_3 Sc) C_i^j + (r_2 + \chi r_3 Sc) C_{i+1}^j - Kr Sc \Delta t (C_i^j)^n \quad (15)$$

$$-q_2 r_1 \theta_{i-1}^{j+1} + (Pr + 2q_2 r_1) \theta_i^{j+1} - q_2 r_1 \theta_{i+1}^{j+1} = q_2 r_2 \theta_{i-1}^j + (Pr - 2q_2 r_2 - \chi r_3 Pr + r_7) \theta_i^j + (q_2 r_2 + \chi r_3 Pr) \theta_{i+1}^j - \ddagger r_6 (\theta_{i+1}^j - \theta_{i-1}^j)^2 + q_2 r_6 Pr Ec (U_{i+1}^j - U_{i-1}^j)^2 + QC_i^j \quad (16)$$

where $r_1 = \frac{r \Delta t}{(\Delta y)^2}$, $r_2 = \frac{(1-r) \Delta t}{(\Delta y)^2}$, $r_3 = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y}$, $r_4 = \Delta t M$, $r_5 = \frac{\Delta t}{K}$, $r_6 = \frac{\Delta t}{4(\Delta y)^2}$, $r_7 = (H-N) \Delta t$,

$q_1 = 1 - \ddagger \theta_i^j$, $q_2 = 1 + \ddagger \theta_i^j$. The mesh sizes along y- direction and time t-direction are Δy and Δt respectively while the index i refers to space y and j refers to time t . The finite difference equations (14) - (16) at every internal nodal point on a particular n-level

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constitute a tridiagonal system of equations which are solved by using the Thomas algorithm.

In each time step, the concentration and temperature profiles have been computed first from equations (15) and (16). The computed values are used to obtain the velocity profile which meets the convergence criteria.

The shear stress, rate of heat and mass transfer in terms of skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number respectively are given by

$$C_f = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, \quad Nu = \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, \quad Sh = \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}$$

Results and Discussion

The numerical solutions are simulated for different values of the Prandtl number (Pr), Schmidt number (Sc), Eckert number (Ec), thermal Grashof number (Gr), mass Grashof number (Gc), radiation (N), magnetic field (M), porosity (K), thermal conductivity (\dagger), suction (r), reaction order (n), chemical reaction (Kr), heat source/absorption (H) and radiation absorption (Q) parameters. The following parameter values are fixed throughout the calculations except where otherwise stated, Pr = 0.71, Sc = 0.62, Ec = 0.01, M = 1, K = 1, Gr = 1, Gc = 1, N = 0.1, $r = 1$, $\dagger = 0.1$, Kr = 0.1, H = 1, Q = 1 and n = 1.

Figures 1 to 11 illustrate the velocity profiles for different values of Prandtl number (Pr = 0.71, 1.63, 3, 7), thermal Grashof number (Gr = 1, 3, 5, 7), mass Grashof number (Gc = 1, 3, 5, 7), magnetic field (M = 1, 5, 10, 15), porosity (K = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7), suction ($r = 2, 4, 6, 8$), Schmidt number (Sc = 0.62, 0.78, 1, 2.63), radiation (N = 10, 20, 30, 40), chemical reaction (Kr = 1, 10, 20, 30), heat source (H = 1, 3, 5, 7) and radiation absorption (Q = 1, 3, 5, 7).

Figure 1 shows that the velocity decreases with increasing Prandtl number. Likewise, Figure 2 indicates that, the velocity decrease with an increase in the magnetic field parameter. But, Figure 3 pointed that, the velocity increase whenever porosity parameter increases. Similarly, Figure 4 shows that, the velocity increase with increasing thermal Grashof number just like Figure 5 which reveals that, the velocity increase when the mass Grashof number increased. While from Figure 6, it found that, the velocity decrease with increasing suction parameter. Similarly, Figure 7 depicts that

the velocity decreases with increasing Schmidt number. Likewise, Figure 8 indicates that, the velocity decrease with an increase in the radiation parameter. Also Figure 9 pointed that, the velocity decreases whenever the chemical reaction parameter increases. However, Figure 10 shows that, the velocity increase with increasing heat source parameter just like Figure 11 which founds that, the velocity increase when the radiation absorption parameter increased.

Figures 12 to 14 represent the concentration profiles for different values of Schmidt number ($Sc = 0.62, 0.78, 1, 2.63$), suction ($r = 2, 4, 6, 8$) and chemical reaction ($Kr = 1, 10, 20, 30$) parameters as in Figures 12, 13 and 14 respectively.

In Figure 12, it is observed that, the concentration decrease with increase in the Schmidt number and likewise Figure 13 shows that, the concentration decrease with increase in the suction parameter. Similarly, Figure 14 reveals that, the concentration decrease whenever the chemical reaction parameter increased.

The temperature profiles have been studied and illustrated in Figures 15 to 20 for different values of Prandtl number ($Pr = 0.71, 1.63, 3, 7$), radiation ($N = 10, 20, 30, 40$), suction ($r = 2, 4, 6, 8$), thermal conductivity ($\dagger = 0.01, 0.1, 0.5, 1$), heat source ($H = 1, 3, 5, 7$) and radiation absorption ($Q = 1, 3, 5, 7$), parameters shown in Figures 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 respectively.

Figure 15 shows that, the temperature decrease with increase in the Prandtl number. Also, Figure 16 indicates that the temperature decrease with increase of the radiation parameter and similarly for the suction parameter, Figure 17 reveals that, the temperature decrease whenever the suction parameter increased. Likewise, Figure 18 found that, the temperature decrease with increase of the thermal conductivity parameter. However, Figure 19 depicts that, the temperature increase with increase of heat source parameter as in the case of Figure 20 which indicates that the temperature increase with increase of the radiation absorption parameter.

Tables 1 to 3 are for the skin friction coefficient, Nusselt number and Sherwood number for the numerical solution.

Table 1 illustrates the skin friction for different values of thermal and mass Grashoff numbers Gr and Gc , heat source H , radiation absorption Q and thermal conductivity \dagger parameters. From the Table, it is noticed that increase in all the parameters increases the skin friction.

Table 2 represents the Nusselt number for different values of Prandtl number Pr , thermal conductivity \dagger , heat source H and radiation absorption Q parameters. In the Table, it is observed that the Nusselt number decrease with increasing Prandtl number and thermal conductivity but increase when heat source and radiation absorption parameters increased.

Moreover, the Sherwood number is demonstrated in Table 3 for different values of Schmidt number Sc , chemical reaction Kr and suction Γ parameters. Results from the Table shows that the Sherwood number decreases with increase of any of the parameters.

Figure 1: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Pr.

Figure 2: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of M.

Figure 3: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of K.

Figure 4: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Gr.

Figure 5: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Gc.

Figure 6: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of r .

Figure 7: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Sc .

Figure 8: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of N .

Figure 9: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Kr .

Figure 10: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of H .

Figure 11: Variation of Velocity against y for different values of Q .

Figure 12: Variation of Concentration against y for different values of Sc.

Figure 13: Variation of Concentration against y for different values of r .

Figure 14: Variation of Concentration against y for different values of Kr.

Figure 15: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of Pr .

Figure 16: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of N .

Figure 17: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of r .

Figure 18: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of T .

Figure 19: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of H.

Figure 20: Variation of Temperature against y for different values of Q.

Table 1: Skin friction for different values of Gr, Gc, H, Q and \dagger .

Gr	Gc	H	Q	\dagger	C_f
1	1	1	1	0.1	4.5036
3	1	1	1	0.1	12.8113
1	3	1	1	0.1	5.2033
1	1	3	1	0.1	5.3289
1	1	1	3	0.1	12.6963
1	1	1	1	0.5	5.9123

Table 2: Nusselt number for different values of Pr, \dagger , H and Q.

Pr	\dagger	H	Q	Nu
0.71	0.1	1	1	58.2929
1.63	0.1	1	1	46.8744
0.71	1	1	1	35.0160
0.71	0.1	3	1	70.2606
0.71	0.1	1	3	176.5529

Table 3: Sherwood number for different values of Sc, Kr and r .

Sc	Kr	r	-(Sh)
0.62	0.1	1	1.1604
1	0.1	1	1.5955
0.62	10	1	2.7806
0.62	0.1	4	2.4522

Conclusions

Heat source and radiation absorption effects on heat mass transfer flow with temperature dependent viscosity and thermal conductivity were studied. Numerical solutions obtained are presented in graphs and tables for the fluid flow. Among other things, the result shows that both the heat source and radiation absorption parameters, enhanced the temperature as well as the velocity of the fluid.

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